

FEATURES OF ENSURING THE RELIABILITY OF CENTRALIZED IMEI DATABASES (CEIR) IN TELECOMMUNICATION SYSTEMS

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Abstract. *The article examines the features of ensuring the reliability of centralized IMEI databases (CEIR) in modern telecommunication systems. It is shown that CEIR is a critical element of the global infrastructure for mobile device identification, ensuring the consistency and accuracy of registration data at the international level. The architecture and functions of CEIR are analyzed, including interaction with national EIR databases, data normalization and deduplication procedures, and mechanisms for blocking illegal devices [1]. Reliability indicators $P(t)$, $F(t)$, $f(t)$, and K_G are considered, along with methods of their application for assessing the fault tolerance of data storage and processing systems. A comparative analysis of approaches to improving reliability is carried out, including replication, blockchain, Big Data, and machine learning [2–4]. Particular attention is given to issues of scalability and cybersecurity threats under conditions of exponential growth in the number of connections. The conclusion emphasizes the necessity of combined strategies to improve CEIR reliability, taking into account the prospects of 6G/NTN development.*

Keywords: *CEIR, EIR, IMEI, reliability, fault tolerance, MTBF, cybersecurity, IoT, Big Data, Blockchain, 6G/NTN*

Introduction

With the increasing number of mobile terminals supporting multi-band communication standards (2G–5G/6G, IoT, NTN), centralized IMEI CEIR (Central Equipment Identity Register) databases have become a key element in ensuring the security and resilience of telecommunication networks. CEIR functions as a global repository of mobile device identifiers, synchronized with national EIR (Equipment Identity Register) databases of telecom operators [5]. Its reliability directly affects such parameters as the stability of mobile networks, the effectiveness of combating fraud (cloning, gray imports, theft) [1], the correct operation of eSIM/iSIM services and massive IoT connections, and the protection of critical infrastructure from failures and attacks [6–8].

Method

A comprehensive methodology was used to conduct the study, including technical analysis, comparative approach and forecasting. The methodology covers several stages:

- analysis of regulatory and technical documentation: a study of international standards, recommendations and specifications published by 3GPP, ETSI, GSMA, ITU organizations regulating the structure, purpose and use of EIR/CEIR was conducted.
- an analysis of the architectures of the national EIR and centralized CEIR was performed;
- analysis of modern technological trends.

Architecture and purpose of EIR and CEIR

In modern telecommunication systems, the management of mobile device identification is carried out using IMEI registers. At the national level, EIRs are used, which are integrated into the networks of telecom operators (Figure 1).

The EIR is an operator or national IMEI database that performs online IMEI verification during device registration in the network (attach/TAU/CM service request), maintains status lists (White/Grey/Black lists) [1], exports/imports records, and synchronizes with the centralized CEIR.

Figure 1. Architecture of the national EIR

Each EIR stores information on three categories of devices [9]:

- 1. White list** – devices with valid IMEIs permitted for use;
- 2. Black list** – stolen, blocked, or illegal devices;
- 3. Grey list** – devices with suspicious or invalid IMEIs requiring additional verification.

At the global level, the centralized CEIR database (Central Equipment Identity Register) aggregates information from all national EIRs and ensures data synchronization (Figure 2).

CEIR serves as a global register that aggregates records from multiple EIRs, performs reception and normalization of data streams from operators/regulators, record matching and deduplication, global indexing and IMEI API verification, fraud analytics (rule-based and machine learning) [1, 4], and redistribution of black/grey lists.

CEIR performs the critical function of ensuring that a device blocked in one country cannot be used in another. Thus, CEIR acts as a global filter and trust system, ensuring consistency among local operator registers.

CEIR is the central link in the global IMEI registration system, ensuring the integrity, security, and reliability of telecommunication network operations. Without CEIR, effective counteraction against illegal terminals and the establishment of a trusted mobile communication ecosystem would be impossible. Figure 3 illustrates the role of the centralized IMEI CEIR database in the device registration system [1].

A user device transmits its IMEI to the operator's network, where it is recorded in the national EIR database. The data are then synchronized with the centralized CEIR, which ensures international exchange and control over IMEI uniqueness. This structure makes it possible to detect cloned devices, prevent fraud, and maintain database consistency at the global level [10].

Table 1 presents a comparison of the key parameters of the two levels of IMEI registration systems — EIR and CEIR [1].

Figure 2. Architecture of the centralized CEIR

Figure 3. Model of interaction between national EIRs and the centralized CEIR database with IMEI record synchronization

Table 1. Comparative characteristics of the national EIR database and the centralized CEIR

№	Parameter	EIR (national database)	CEIR (centralized database)
1	Scope of coverage	National	International
2	Data volume	Up to tens of millions of records	Hundreds of millions – billions of records
3	Main function	IMEI control in national network	Global IMEI check and blocking
4	Failure Resistance	Average	Critically High

5	Risk of overload	Low	High
6	Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF)	Days/weeks (local bases)	Months/years
7	Probability of failure-free operation $P(t)$	$P(t)=e^{-\lambda t}$, for EIR λ is greater (reliability is lower), for CEIR λ is less (reliability is higher)	
8	Availability coefficient (K_A)	0,95–0,98	0,999–0,9999

Thus, CEIR requires stricter measures to ensure reliability and availability than national EIRs, since global protection against IMEI cloning, gray imports, and fraud depends on its correct functioning, and its reliability and fault tolerance are of higher priority compared to EIR.

Despite international efforts, CEIR faces a number of challenges:

1. IMEI cloning. Attackers can reprogram a device by assigning it a valid IMEI. Blocking at the level of one country does not guarantee prevention of use in another [1, 11].

2. Scalability and overload. The growing number of connected devices (smartphones, tablets, IoT devices, eSIM/iSIM terminals) leads to exponential growth of records in the database. Modern CEIRs contain hundreds of millions of records, requiring high performance of storage and search systems [12–16].

3. Errors and data duplication. During synchronization between EIR and CEIR, situations may arise when the same device is registered with errors or duplicates, which reduces system accuracy [12–16].

4. Information security threats. As a centralized system, CEIR is a potential target for cyberattacks: DDoS attacks, SQL injections, and unauthorized copying of the database [6–8], [17, 18].

Modern technical solutions to ensure reliability

One of the key issues is ensuring reliability. The reliability of centralized IMEI CEIR databases represents an integral property of the system, expressing its ability, within a specified time interval, to provide continuous, correct, and secure functioning of processes for registering, storing, processing, and exchanging mobile device identification data [2, 3]. The relevance of ensuring high CEIR reliability is due to the fact that this system plays a crucial role in preventing fraud using cloned and stolen devices, supports the resilience of national telecommunication infrastructure, ensures trust in international exchange of registration data (GSMA IMEI DB), and provides scalability under exponential growth of 5G/6G, IoT, and eSIM/iSIM connections [19].

For describing the reliability of data storage systems, the following indicators are used: probability of failure-free operation, failure function, failure density distribution, and availability coefficient.

The probability of failure-free operation $P(t)$ is the probability that the system will perform its specified functions without failure for a time t , starting from the moment it is put into operation. It is expressed as:

$$P(t) = P\{T > t\}, \quad (1)$$

where T is a random variable characterizing time to failure;

$P\{T > t\}$ is the probability that the time to failure exceeds the given interval t .

The failure function $F(t)$ is the probability that the system (or element) will fail no later than time t :

$$F(t) = 1 - P(t) \quad (2)$$

The failure density distribution $f(t)$ is a function that characterizes the probability that a failure will occur in a small time interval $[t, t+\Delta t]$:

$$f(t) = \frac{dF(t)}{dt} \quad (3)$$

The availability coefficient (K_A) - is the probability that the system is in an operational state at an arbitrary moment when its functions are required.

It is defined through the mean time between failures (MTBF) and the mean time to repair (MTTR):

$$K_A = \frac{MTBF}{MTBF + MTTR} \quad (4)$$

Indicators (1)-(4) are applicable to assessing the fault tolerance of CEIR databases, where a failure is understood as loss of access, data integrity violation, or synchronization error [2, 3]. For information and communication systems, the exponential law of failure distribution is most commonly applied. In this case, for the exponential distribution:

$$P(t) = e^{-\lambda t} \quad (5)$$

$$f(t) = \lambda e^{-\lambda t} \quad (6)$$

where λ - is the failure rate.

Figure 4 shows the reliability functions $P(t)$, $F(t)$, $f(t)$ for an exponential distribution of failures.

Figure 4. Dependencies $P(t)$, $F(t)$ and $f(t)$ for exponential distribution of failures

The curve $P(t)$ characterizes the probability of failure-free operation and decreases exponentially over time, reflecting the decline in system reliability; $F(t)$ represents the failure function and increases monotonically, indicating the probability that a failure will occur by time t ; $f(t)$ corresponds to the failure density distribution and reflects the probability of a failure occurring within a small time interval. Its maximum value occurs at the initial moment of time; after which it decreases.

In global practice, the following approaches to ensuring CEIR reliability have found the widest application [20]:

1. Redundancy and replication. CEIR data are duplicated in several geographically distributed data centers. This increases fault tolerance and reduces the risk of data loss [2, 3].

2. Fraud detection and monitoring systems. Modern CEIRs use algorithms for analyzing device behavior and identifying anomalies, which makes it possible to detect suspicious IMEI registrations in real time [1, 16].

3. Use of Blockchain. A promising direction is the registration of IMEIs in blockchain. This approach ensures immutability of records and transparency of interactions between operators; however, it requires significant computational resources [8].

4. Big Data and machine learning. Big Data technologies are applied to process huge volumes of IMEI records and identify patterns that may indicate fraudulent activity [4, 8].

Table 2. Comparative analysis of existing solutions for ensuring CEIR reliability

№	Solution	Advantages	Disadvantages
1	Classic CEIR architecture	Centralized control, global synchronization	Risk of overload, vulnerability to attacks
2	Replication and backup	High availability and fault tolerance	Infrastructure complexity and cost increase
3	IMEI Blockchain-registration	Data immutability, transparency	High implementation cost and slow processing
4	Big Data + ML analysis	Real-time fraud detection	Requires high computing power

A comparative analysis of existing solutions for ensuring CEIR reliability shows that each of the considered architectural strategies has both advantages and limitations (Table 2). The classical centralized model provides management simplicity and consistency but suffers from risks of overload and attacks. Replication and geo-distributed clusters allow for achieving high availability and minimizing recovery time; however, they require significant resources and complicate consistency management. The use of blockchain technologies ensures transparency and immutability of records, which is particularly important for interagency scenarios, but it is associated with high costs and limited scalability. The introduction of Big Data and ML approaches improves data quality and the efficiency of fraud detection; however, it requires advanced infrastructure and constant model maintenance [21]. Thus, the optimal strategy lies in a combination of solutions that must take into account the specifics of the telecommunication infrastructure and the regulatory requirements of a particular country or region.

Conclusion

The conducted study confirmed that the centralized IMEI CEIR database plays a key role in ensuring the reliability and security of telecommunication systems [1]. CEIR performs functions of global data consolidation, fraud prevention involving cloned IMEIs, maintenance of consistency among national registers, and protection of critical infrastructure. The analysis of reliability indicators has shown that CEIR operation requires stricter requirements for fault tolerance and availability compared to local EIRs. A comparative review of existing architectural solutions revealed that the greatest effect is achieved when traditional methods (replication, redundancy) are combined with new approaches (blockchain, big data analytics, machine learning) [2, 3], [12–15]. In the context of 5G/6G and NTN networks, challenges of scalability and cybersecurity are intensifying. A promising direction is the development of an intelligent and adaptive CEIR model

capable of ensuring trust, resilience, and high reliability under conditions of exponential growth in the number of devices [16].

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